

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GERMPLASM

Some panicle characteristics of rice germplasm from the Northern Province of Sierra Leone

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Characterization of important agronomic traits of locally grown rice germplasm in widely variable ecologies is useful to programs breeding rice for adaptability to diverse environments. The agronomic traits of 150 indigenous lowland rice cultivars collected in the Northern Province of Sierra Leone were evaluated at RRRS.

Variations in panicle length and exertion among the cultivars were low (Table 1). Most cultivars displayed good exertion and low spikelet sterility, and a

Table 1. Variation in panicle length, spikelet sterility, and panicle threshability of indigenous rice cultivars from the Northern Province of Sierra Leone, 1987.

Character	Varietal frequency (no.) on the SES ^a scale of 1-9				
	13579				
Panicle length	110	—	32	—	8
Panicle threshability	9	12	47	92	—
Panicle exertion	115	—	29	—	6
Spikelet sterility	—	87	61	2	—

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Table 2. Variability in 1,000-grain weight of some indigenous rice cultivars from the Northern Province of Sierra Leone, 1987.

1,000-grain weight range (g)	Cultivars (no.)
17.6-19.5	5
19.6-21.6	10
21.7-23.0	19
23.1-25.0	27
25.1-27.0	17
27.1-29.0	36
29.1-31.0	30
31.1-33.0	0
33.1-37.0	6

few nonshattering types were identified. The 1,000-grain weight varied widely (Table 2). That of most cultivars averaged 25-29 g; 5 had very small grains, and 6 had very large grains.

Indigenous rice cultivars in Northern

Sierra Leone thus display wide variability in agronomic traits. After further evaluation, some of these cultivars could be used in breeding programs for specific traits to suit the needs of local farmers. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Possibility of a ratoon crop from photoperiod-insensitive summer rices in calcareous sodic soils of North Bihar, India

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Of the 5.6 million ha under rice cultivation in Bihar, about 1 million ha are under irrigated summer rice cultivation (Mar-Apr to Jun-Jul). Crop harvest in Jul-Aug normally coincides with the monsoon rains, thus leaving little time for land preparation for the main wet season (WS) rice planting. A ratoon crop in WS would reduce labor

costs and free farmers for other field operations.

We studied the ratooning ability of 24 advanced breeding lines Mar-Oct 1984 in an experiment in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Forty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 12-m² plots at 2-3 seedlings/hill, with plants spaced 20 cm between rows and 15 cm within a row. Fertilizer was 80-18-17 kg NPK/ha. N was in 3 splits: 25% basal, 50% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. The soil was calcareous sandy loam with pH 8.4 and EC 0.495 µm.

At maturity the main crop was ratooned by cutting the stalks 15 cm above ground. Immediately after harvest, 40 kg N/ha was applied. Ratooning ability [(number of

Performance of ratoon selections. Pusa, North Bihar, India, 1984 DS and WS.

Variety or line	Ratooning ability (%)	Growth duration			Grain yield		
		Main crop (d)	Ratoon crop (d)	% of main crop	Main crop (t/ha)	Ratoon crop (t/ha)	% of main crop
CR222 MW 10	85.8	132	57	43	2.7	1.6	59
IET7617	88.8	129	57	44	2.5	1.1	44
Rasi	87.8	128	57	45	2.4	1.4	58
RP1664-4461-693-1333	94.9	142	59	42	2.4	1.7	71
IR19743-25-2-2-3-1	59.4	129	49	38	2.3	1.1	48
RP1158-172-1	94.0	129	59	46	2.3	1.3	57
IET7613	94.5	133	59	45	2.2	0.8	36
CR215-55-44-1	68.8	128	49	38	2.2	1.3	59
IET3279	91.8	130	61	47	2.1	1.4	67
IR5B-36-70-1	74.3	133	57	43	2.1	1.1	52

regenerated hills in the ratoon crop/total hills in the main crop) × 100] was evaluated 4 wk after main crop cutting.

Only 10 of 24 breeding lines showed regeneration. Ratooning ability varied from 59.4% to 94.9%, and ratoon growth duration from 49 to 61 d (see table). Thus, ratoon crop duration was 38-47% of that of the main crop. Ratoon height was slightly reduced but

ratoon grain yield did not significantly differ. RP1664-4461-693-1333 had the highest ratoon yield (1.7 t/ha), and IET7613 the lowest (0.8 t/ha) (see table). The reduction in ratoon grain yield was due primarily to smaller and fewer panicles.

The ratoon crop harvest — first week Oct — left ample time for the farmers to

plant another oilseed crop (rape or mustard), winter maize, or potato. But before adoption of rice ratooning in WS, the benefit-cost ratios of different cropping patterns — summer rice - ratoon rice - oilseed (or maize or potato) and summer rice - WS rice - oilseed (or potato or maize) — should be compared. □

Sequential tiller separation - a method for rapid rice seed multiplication

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To increase seed production of elite rice cultivars in a single season, we tried transplanting single tillers after repeatedly separating tillers. Five-day-old seedlings of 4 rice cultivars — PR103, PR106, PR109, and Basmati 370 — were transplanted 30 May 1986 at 40 seedlings each with 15- × 30-cm spacing. Each seedling developed 3-6 tillers within 18 d.

Effect of sequential tiller separation and transplanting on number of plants, yield, and seed multiplication ratio. Ludhiana, India, 1986 summer.

Split no.	Plants (no.)	Seed yield (kg/ha)	Seed multiplication ratio
<i>PR 103</i>			
0	10	1	200
1	40	5	781
2	116	10	1569
3	416	20	3302
<i>PR 106</i>			
0	10	1	250
1	52	6	1235
2	179	12	2598
3	659	42	9332
<i>PR 109</i>			
0	10	1	250
1	62	8	1468
2	225	20	3418
3	953	55	9705
<i>Basmati 370</i>			
0	10	1	125
1	38	5	481
2	97	9	931
3	390	19	1985

Thirty seedlings of each cultivar were uprooted and their tillers separated with a sharp razor (split 1). The separated tillers were retransplanted at 15- × 30-cm spacing in such a way that all tillers of every 10 uprooted seedlings formed one strip, for 3 strips/variety. The schematic propagation of PR109 is illustrated in the figure.

Ten days after the second transplanting, two strips of each variety were uprooted and the tillers separated (split 2). Those tillers were retransplanted 3 Jul. On 18 Jul, seedlings from one strip/cultivar were uprooted, tillers separated, and transplanted (split 3). Purple colored cultivar R575 was transplanted around all strips of all cultivars to control border effect.

The effect of sequential tiller splitting and transplanting on number of plants, seed yield, and seed multiplication ratio is given in the table. Maximum number of plants was from the original 10 seedlings of PR109, the minimum was with Basmati 370. Average increase in number of plants, irrespective of cultivar, was 62.

Seed yield did not increase in proportion to plant numbers. This may be due to reduced size and length of panicles, higher floret sterility, and reduced number of effective tillers. Increase in seed yield ranged from 16 times in Basmati 370 to 39 times in PR109, with an average of 27 times that of control.

Highest seed yield after the last split was 55 kg in PR109. Basmati 370 yielded 19 kg seed.

Sequential splitting and transplanting of rice tillers could help in rapid multiplication of elite and newly developed cytogenetic male sterile lines

for hybrid rice production. Small quantities of experimental hybrid rice seed also could be multiplied for testing across several locations in a single season. □

Schematic of single season vegetative propagation of rice cultivar PR109. Ludhiana, India, 1986 summer.